

Facile synthesis of chalcone derivatized hexatrienes via Stobbe condensation

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Abstract : In course of studies on the solvent-free Stobbe condensation, the acid-esters, methyl hydrogen 2-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butanedioate and methyl hydrogen 2-alkylidene-3-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butanedioate were synthesized, which could be successfully saponified to the corresponding diacid; 2-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butane dioic acid and 2-alkylidene-3-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butane dioic acid respectively. The diacids were cyclized to corresponding anhydrides, which were taken for photochromic studies.

Keywords : Stobbe condensation, solvent-free, photochromic studies.

Introduction

Stobbe condensation, an important C–C bond forming reaction¹⁻⁵, occurs in chalcones^{6,7} with dimethyl succinate by classical method⁸ as well as in a simple, convenient, economical and hazard-free manner⁹.

Present work describes the use of a bulky α,β -unsaturated aromatic ketone, namely, 1,3-diphenylprop-2-ene-1-one (**1**) (prepared by Claisen-Schmidt condensation of acetophenone and benzaldehyde using ethanolic NaOH) in the classical as well as solvent-free Stobbe condensation. Under green context, the ketone (**1**) reacted with dimethyl succinate smoothly giving **2a** in better yields (85%) as compared to that in classical method (78%) (Scheme 1) (Table 1). The half ester **2a** on saponification with 8% alcoholic KOH followed by acidification gave the diacid **2c** as shining yellow crystals on recrystallisation from benzene-*n*-hexane. The diacid **2c** was cyclized with conc. H₂SO₄ at 0 °C into a cyclic ketone **4a**, which enolised to phenol **4b**.

Previously¹⁰, solvent-free Stobbe mono-condensations as well as di-condensations were successfully done using different aliphatic (acetone, ethyl methyl ketone) and aromatic ketone (acetophenone).

Di-condensation reactions were tried using the diester **2b** with different aromatic aldehydes when the half-esters **3a-c** were obtained in better yields (80–85%) in solvent

Table 1. Physical characterization data

Compd.	Mol. formulae	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)		Equivalent weight Found (Calcd.)
			Classical	Green	
2a	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄	196	78	85	320.5 (322.3)
2c	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₄	198	79	– ^a	155.9 (154.1)
3a	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₄	211	64	80	408.9 (410.43)
3b	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₅	200	73	85	438.1 (440.4)
3c	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ O ₅	189	72	81	397.5 (400.4)
3d	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₄	215	62	– ^a	195.2 (198.2)
3e	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₅	205	72	– ^a	210.9 (213.2)
3f	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₅	192	84	– ^a	195.2 (193.2)
4	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₃	200	40	– ^b	288.35 (290.00)

^aProducts were obtained in quantitative yield after saponification.

^bProducts were obtained in quantitative yield after cyclization.

free method than in classical method (64–73%). On saponification, corresponding diacids **3d-f** were obtained, which could not be cyclised with conc. H₂SO₄ at 0 °C. However, these diacids could be successfully cyclodehydrated with acetyl chloride upon reflux for three hours into corresponding anhydrides **5a-c** being proved by their IR spectra (Table 3). Structural elucidation of all the half-esters and diacids have been accomplished by UV¹¹, IR¹² and NMR spectra¹³ (Tables 2, 3 and 4).

Products **5a-c** were taken for photochromic studies, using immersion well photochemical reactor. Upon irradiation at 256 nm in the reactor, these anhydrides showed a wavelength shift of about 20–45 nm.

Scheme 1

Table 2. UV data

Compd.	λ_{max} (nm)	log ϵ
2a	240	3.35
2c	226, 262	3.33, 3.23
3a	379, 221	4.623, 4.621
3b	232, 380	4.65, 4.66
3c	207, 245	4.94, 4.45
3d	296	3.85
3e	250, 326	4.62, 4.63
3f	224, 274	3.16, 3.20
4	215, 272, 285	4.5, 4.8, 3.3

Results and discussion

Solvent-free method of Stobbe condensation was superior to classical method with respect to product yield.

Both in the mono-condensation and di-condensation reactions, the half esters 2a and 3a-c, respectively were obtained irrespective of the method (solvent-free or classical) used.

Interestingly, a cyclic ketone 4a was synthesized from the diacid 2c using conc. H_2SO_4 at 0°C .

The formation of 4a can also be well explained by following mechanism (Scheme 2).

The cyclized product was found to exist as an equilibrium mixture of 4a and 4b with the latter predominating. This is supported by ^1H NMR spectrum of 4 in which peak at δ 7.56 for phenolic proton as singlet was due to enolic form 4b and an additional small peak at δ 2.51 (singlet) was due to methylene protons showing the presence of minor population of keto form 4a. On the basis of

Table 3. IR data, ν (cm^{-1})

Compd.	CO unsaturated	CO unsaturated	C-O	Cyclic	Phenolic	C-O-C
	ester	acid				
2a	1693.7	1627.6	1177	-	-	-
2c	-	1674.3	1066	-	-	-
3a	1715.1	1652.7	1224.2	-	-	-
3b	1709.2	1648.1	1124	-	-	-
3c	1712.5	1653.5	1195	-	-	-
3d	-	1643.5	1155.7	-	-	-
3e	-	1674.5	1197.4	-	-	-
3f	-	1724.7	1197.6	-	-	-
4	-	-	-	1690	3400	-
5a	-	-	-	-	-	1781, 1844
5b	-	-	-	-	-	1740, 1814
5c	-	-	-	-	-	1740, 1825

integration values, i.e. for phenolic proton 3.7 cm and for methylene protons 1.8 cm, the keto-enol ratio was found to be 20 : 80. IR spectrum of **4** also depicts the presence of absorption peaks at 1690 cm^{-1} due to cyclic ketonic carbonyl and 3400 cm^{-1} due to phenolic OH group. Similarly, in UV spectrum, two intense peaks at 215 nm and 272 nm (due to OH substituted benzene) and a moderate peak at 285 nm (for cyclic α , β -unsaturated ketone) were observed.

When studied the photochromic behaviour on anhydrides **5a-c**, it was observed that, anhydride **5c** showed a maximum wavelength shift of 46 nm; while the other two

anhydrides **5a** and **5b** exhibited a moderate shift of about 15–20 nm (Table 5). These results are in good agreement with the Santiago and Becker mechanism¹⁴ as proved earlier.

Experimental

NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS an internal standard, IR spectra in KBr pellets and Nujol-mull and UV-Vis spectra in spectroscopic ethanol on a DMS-80 (Varian) spectrophotometer. Immersion well photochemical reactor (Model IWQ1) was used for the photo-irradiation experiments.

Compd.	Table 4. ¹ H NMR data, δ (ppm)						
	Aromatic	Vinyl	HC=CH	Furyl	OCH ₃	CH ₂	Phenolic OH
2a	7.26-7.3 (5H, m), 7.31-7.36 (5H, m)	-	7.06-7.14 (2H, m)	-	3.38 (3H, s)	2.49 (2H, s)	-
2c	6.99-7.10 (5H, m), 7.11-7.52 (5H, m)	-	7.53-7.63 (2H, m)	-	-	2.17 (2H, s)	-
3a	7.5-7.54 (5H, m), 7.7-7.74 (5H, m), 7.2-7.25 (5H, m)	7.35 (1H, s)	7.95-8.00 (2H, m)	-	3.48 (3H, s)	-	-
3b	7.5-7.53 (5H, m), 7.75-7.78 (5H, m), 7.54-7.55 (4H, m)	7.36 (1H, s)	7.29-7.30 (2H, m)	-	3.5 (3H, s), 3.17 (3H, s)	-	-
3c	7.09-7.16 (5H, m), 7.29-7.34 (5H, m)	7.64 (1H, s)	7.55-7.56 (2H, m)	6.4-6.9 (3H, m)	3.69 (3H, s)	-	-
3d	7.5-7.6 (5H, m), 7.8-8.0 (5H, m), 8.54-8.55 (5H, m)	7.53 (1H, s)	7.63-7.65 (2H, m)	-	-	-	-
3e	7.56-7.57 (5H, m), 7.58-7.59 (5H, m), 7.4-7.5 (4H, m)	7.58 (1H, s)	7.90-7.94 (2H, m)	-	3.03 (3H, s)	-	-
3f	7.51-7.53 (5H, m), 7.71-7.73 (5H, m)	7.55 (1H, s)	7.20-7.24 (2H, m)	6.8-7.0 (3H, m)	-	-	-
4	7.46-7.47 (12H, m)	-	-	-	-	2.51 (2H, s)	7.56 (1H, s)

Table 5. Wavelength shift (nm)

Compd.	Wavelength λ_{\max} (nm)		Wavelength shift in λ_{\max} (nm)
	Before irradiation	After irradiation	
5a	218	239	21
5b	213	228	15
5c	260	306	46

Methyl hydrogen 2-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butanedioate (2a) :

Classical method :

A mixture of dimethyl succinate (1.46 g, 10 mmol) and 1,3-diphenylprop-2-ene-1-one (**1**) (2.08 g, 10 mmol) was added to a well stirred solution of tertiary butanolic potassium tert.-butoxide prepared by dissolving potassium (1 g) in dry tertiary butanol (25 mL). After stirring for 1 h at room temperature and usual working up⁸, half ester, **2a** (m.p. 196 °C) was obtained in 78% yield when recrystallised from benzene-*n*-hexane.

Solvent free method :

In solvent-free method, a neat mixture of dimethyl succinate (1.46 g, 10 mmol) and ketone (**1**) (2.08 g, 10 mmol) was taken in a dry mortar and to it dried solid potassium tert.-butoxide (1.13 g, 10 mmol) was added and grounded with a pestle at room temperature for 10 min. The reaction mixture was exposed to air. After usual work-up⁵ and recrystallisation from benzene-*n*-hexane, **2a** was obtained in 85% yield.

2a was esterified quantitatively by diazomethane¹⁵ to the diester; dimethyl 2-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butanedioate **2b**.

Methyl hydrogen 2-alkylidene-3-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butanedioate (3a-c) :

Classical method :

A mixture of the diester **2b** (3.36 g, 10 mmol) and benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 10 mmol) was added to a well stirred solution of tertiary butanolic potassium tert.-butoxide prepared by dissolving potassium (1 g) in dry tertiary butanol (25 mL). After stirring for 1 h at room temperature and usual work up⁸ and recrystallisation from benzene pet. ether gave half ester; methyl hydrogen 2-benzylidene-3-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butanedioate, **3a** (m.p. 211 °C) in 64% yield.

Solvent free method :

The yield was improved to 80% when the same reaction was carried out by solvent-free method using **2b** (3.36 g, 10 mmol), benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 10 mmol) and potassium tert.-butoxide (1.13 g, 10 mmol).

Similarly, anisaldehyde (1.36 g, 10 mmol) and furfural (0.96 g, 10 mmol) gave the half esters methyl hydrogen 2-(4-methoxybenzylidene)-3-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butanedioate (**3b**) and methyl hydrogen 2-furanylidene-3-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butanedioate (**3c**), respectively.

Hydrolysis of 2a and 3a-c :

Half ester **2a** or **3a-c** (5 mmol) was added to 8% alcoholic KOH (30 mL) and refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was filtered, the filtrate was cooled to 0 °C and acidified with ice-cool conc. HCl to give diacid 2-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butanedioic acid (**2c**) or 2-alkylidene-3-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)butanedioic acid (**3d-f**) respectively, which were recrystallised from ethanol-water to produce shining yellow needles.

Cyclization of 2c :

In a dry and clean conical flask, diacid **2c** (0.3 g) was dissolved in ether (5 mL) and cooled to 0 °C. Ice-cold conc. H₂SO₄ (3 mL) was added dropwise and kept at 0 °C for 24 h. The mixture was then poured on crushed ice, when the solid separated, recrystallized from benzene-*n*-hexane and identified as a mixture of the tautomer; 2,4-diphenyl-5-oxo-1,3-cyclohexadiene-1-carboxylic acid (**4a**) and 2,4-diphenyl-5-hydroxybenzoic acid (**4b**) from spectral analysis.

3-Alkylidene-4-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)tetrahydrofuran-2,5-dione (5a-c) :

Compound **3d** (1 g) was dissolved in benzene (10 mL) and to it was carefully added acetyl chloride (10 mL) and the reaction mixture was refluxed gently for 3 h on oil-bath. The reaction mixture was filtered hot. The filtrate was cooled to room temperature to afford a solid, which on recrystallization from a mixture of benzene-*n*-hexane produced shining yellow crystals of 3-benzylidene-4-(1,3-diphenylpropen-3-ylidene)tetrahydrofuran-2,5-dione (**5a**) in 62% yield (m.p. 230 °C). Similarly, the anhydrides **5b** (m.p. 220 °C) and **5c** (m.p. 198 °C) were synthesized from their respective di-carboxylic acids **3e** and **3f**.

Typical procedure for photo-irradiation reactions :

A 10 mg of anhydride **5a** was dissolved in 100 ml specanol (prepared by refluxing dry ethanol with Zn and KOH and subsequent distillation). 50 ml of the solution was exposed to UV radiation in an UV-Visible spectrophotometer at different wavelengths and λ_{\max} was noted. It was, then, irradiated in immersion well photo-reactor for 20 min at 254 nm with due care and immediately the irradiated sample was scanned for λ_{\max} in the spectrophotometer. The shift in λ_{\max} was observed. In the same way, other anhydrides **5b** and **5c** were analyzed for wavelength shifts (Table 5).

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